

Detection of food-drug interactions using natural language processing techniques in the context of FNS-Cloud project

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Health and nutrition are intimately related. The consumption of specialized foods with the goal of improving health, preventing disease or as alternative complementary treatment has risen in the last years (Mongioli et al., 2017). This, coupled with an increasingly aging and medicated population means an increased risk of potential food drug interactions (FDI) (Choi et al, 2017). It is necessary for clinicians and dietitians to have access to high quality available data in this area to communicate potential FDIs to their patients which can seek alternative treatments in the form of dietary changes, with potentially disastrous consequences to their health. A problem that plagues the food science domain is the fragmentation and lack of standards of its resources. The Food Nutrition Security cloud project (FNS cloud) was launched to federate existing resources in the food domain. One of its goals is to provide a centralized information portal for food-diet-drug interactions. To this end, we are developing an NLP pipeline to extract food drug interactions mentioned in scientific article abstracts, with the intent of creating a web application for clinicians to use when searching for FDIs. Food drug interaction extraction is formulated as a relationship extraction problem. First, entities related to food, drugs and food chemicals are recognized in a sentence and for every pair of food-drug entities it is determined if a relationship of “interaction” exists between them. The pipeline's main hurdle is the poor amount of labelled text data for the food domain, which is overcome with the combination of labelled data from different sources, ontologies, and food composition databases. The pipeline presented uses a mixture of deep learning, dictionary-based and ontology-based approaches for the recognition and linking of food, chemical and drug entities in the text, and in linking chemicals to foods. Recognition of abbreviations and co-reference resolution approaches are also used to link all different expressions of the same entity together. A transfer learning approach is used to recognize FDI, by training a deep learning relationship extractor to recognize anonymized drug-drug interactions on a corpus of drug-drug interactions (Herrero-Zazo et al., 2013) and using it on anonymized food drug interactions.

References:

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